

FINAL REPORT

1 General information

DFG-Nr:	MA 9235/1-1
Projektnr:	446268581
Titel:	Vessel distance mapping: Quantification of subcortical arterial and venous vascular patterns to study their interdependency
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Co-Pis:	Stefanie Schreiber, Oliver Speck

2 Summary

To function, the brain requires the supply and draining of blood through the arterial and venous vasculature, respectively. These tree-like vessel networks have complex branching patterns and with decreasing vessel diameter the branching becomes more and more subject-specific, rendering comparisons non-trivial. The aim of this project was to develop a novel tool to quantify the vessel trajectory with respect to the surrounding brain structure and find clusters of similar vessel trajectories across subjects which we call vessel patterns. To that end, Vessel Distance Mapping (VDM) was developed and applied to find distinct arterial and venous vessel patterns within the putamen, a subcortical structure in the brain. To depict small vessels (vessel diameter $<0.5\text{mm}$) within the putamen non-invasively high-resolution Magnetic Resonance Imaging was used.

In essence, VDMs compute and display the Euclidian distance of each point in space to its closest vessel. Therefore, this simplistic and easily comprehensible metric provides maps quantifying the spatial proximity of the vasculature, inspired by the idea that closeness correlates with relevance.

Within the putamen, we found distinct arterial and venous patterns. If these vessel patterns represent vascular reserve mechanisms in pathology is currently evaluated in a follow-up study. Further, as changes in the vasculature's volume and hemodynamics are the basis for functional MRI, knowledge of the vascular structure is relevant as it may represent a bias in studying the brain's function with MRI.

With VDM-based assessment of MR images, the field can translate the identification of vessel pattern from post mortem studies to non-invasive, in vivo experiments in a robust and quantitative manner with the possibility of tracking patterns longitudinally.

Beyond studying putamen vessel patterns in healthy subjects, we have translated it to quantify vascular resistance and resilience mechanisms in cerebral small vessel disease and

amyotrophic lateral sclerosis by studying arterial vessel patterns in the hippocampus and motor cortex respectively. Further, we envision VDM as a versatile tool for image-based pattern analysis to study the spatial relation of brain vasculature and structure with applications to other imaging modalities such as microscopy.

3 Scientific work and results

The arterial and venous vasculature have a profound effect on the brain's health and function. Subcortical structures, involved in motor, sensory, cognitive and behavioral tasks, are perfused by the major cerebral arteries. The perfusion territories of these large arteries are spatially variable between subjects. This variability influences the organization of small, perforating arteries (vessel diameter $<500 \mu\text{m}$) and we hypothesize that the subcortical perforating vasculature has distinct spatial propagation patterns. Further, these hypothetical vascular patterns were expected on the arterial and venous side, respectively, and we suspected an interdependency of subcortical arterial and venous patterns. To that end, high-resolution Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) was deployed in this project to validate non-invasively this hypothesis in living humans by depicting (WP1), segmenting (WP2), and quantifying (WP3) the arterial and venous patterns of the putamen (chosen as a representative subcortical model region). For the quantification of the vasculature (WP3), vessel distance mapping (VDM) was envisioned to decipher arterial and venous patterns.

WP1 MRI imaging: The planned acquisition of 7T high resolution Time-of-Flight (ToF) angiography and Quantitative Susceptibility Mapping (QSM) for arterial and venous depiction, respectively, was stopped after the piloting phase by the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting 7T MRI research shutdown. Due to the unforeseeable delay caused by the shutdown, in Winter 2020 we decided to re-use openly available data for this project. To this end, part of the StudyForrest data^{1,2} was used. It provided 7T ToF angiography and 3T T2*-weighted data of 20 healthy, young subjects. While part of the data was acquired at 3T and the resolution of the ToF angiography was slightly lower than anticipated in our protocol, depiction of arterial and venous patterns within the putamen was feasible, providing a COVID19-independent alternative for the progress of the project. Nevertheless, the pilot data acquired here further strengthened our expertise in ultra-high resolution ToF angiography and after the shutdown ended, we leveraged this in a collaboration with the MGH Boston (main partners Saskia Bollmann and Jonathan Polimeni) to image the pial arterial vasculature by acquiring the highest resolution ToF angiograms to date (140 μm isotropic voxel size). The results have been published³ and data is openly available⁴.

WP2 Vessel segmentation: As planned, vessel segmentation was performed using a Frangi-filter for vessel enhancement and subsequent thresholding. The source code used was made publicly available⁵ and provides besides the Frangi-filter (based on the scikit-image implementation), and Jerman filter and a novel, fully automated hysteresis thresholding approach (thresholds obtained from multi-class Otsu method)⁶. Further, the ToF angiograms from the StudyForrest data were semi-automatically segmented and with rigorous quality control to create a ground truth. This data was released openly as part of SMILE-UHURA vessel segmentation challenge in 2023 (partners Soumick Chatterjee, Florian Dubost, Andreas Nürnberger)⁷. This ground truth segmentation supplies the demand for an open benchmark data set of high-resolution 3D data (previous benchmarks were either 2D high resolution or 3D low resolution images). Our expertise in high-resolution vessel imaging and Frangi-filter based segmentation were leveraged to develop an openly available, peer-reviewed deep learning vessel segmentation pipeline^{8,9}.

WP3 Vessel Distance Mapping, arterial and venous patterns, and their interdependency: In this work package a novel pattern assessment framework, called Vessel Distance Mapping (VDM), has been developed^{10,11}. The source code is openly available¹². In brief, VDM computes the Euclidian distance of each voxel to its closest segmented vessel, i.e. artery or vein. Hence, VDM provides a 3D-resolved proximity map of the vasculature.

To understand the impact of image resolution on VDM, i.e. the sensitivity of imaging towards small vessel depiction, retrospective down sampling of MR images was performed. There was a linear correlation of voxel size and vessel distance, a favorable behavior of VDM as it potentially enables scaling of VDM results between studies with different imaging resolutions in the future¹³.

For this project, arterial and venous distance maps were computed for each of the 40 putamen (20 subjects, 2 hemispheres) followed by a spatial normalization step (transformation into MNI space). Subsequently the data was automatically clustered. To that end, we developed a novel framework in which an arterial or venous distance map is first translated into a latent space, which we call the vascular fingerprint of an individual putamen. To transform the 3D distance maps into a latent space, the central moments of the distance map is computed. Afterwards, hierarchical clustering using Ward linkage is applied and cluster size (number of patterns found) determined by the maximal Calinski and Harabasz score. As a complementary approach to the unsupervised automatic patterns, together with the medical experts, empirically determined arterial and venous pattern descriptions were established and rated in 40 putamen accordingly.

The detailed methods and results are available as a preprint¹⁴ and can be summarized as follows: (i) Arterial patterns in the putamen are distributed unimodal, i.e. most putamen show

a medium vascularization (normative pattern) with a continuous variation of lower/higher vascularization (represented by fanning of the vessels in the anterior-posterior direction) observed less frequently. (ii) Venous patterns follow a bimodal distribution, i.e. a putamen has either a high or low venous vascularization. Further, there is a putamen-specific variability of drainage by veins reaching the putamen from superior or inferior. (iii) No interdependency between arterial and venous patterns was found, i.e. low arterial vascularization does not correlate with low venous vascularization. While these results are inherently biased by the depicted and segmented vessels, hence depend on imaging resolution, image artifacts, and segmentation quality, they are the first description of distinct arterial and venous pattern in the putamen and challenge the prevalent idea of a single vascular-norm trajectory per brain region. Future studies will assess the contribution of vessel patterns in the putamen to potential resistance or resilience mechanism in pathologies such as cerebral small vessel disease (CSVD). Further, the bias in function MRI (fMRI) due to non-micro-vessel signal contamination will be assessed, higher imaging resolution i.e. layer-specific fMRI, render this contamination more relevant.

Further developments and application of VDM: In parallel to this study, VDM has been applied beyond the initially proposed application. In a project with Berta Garcia-Garcia (joint first authorship with Hendrik Mattern)¹⁵, we develop vessel-specific VDM-metrics as complementary tools to previously published binary expert ratings for the hippocampal vascular supply patterns. The developed VDM-metrics capture vascular resilience mechanisms in CSVD patients. Further, these metrics have been introduced as part of the analysis performed within the project TB04 of the SFB 1436 to quantify the hippocampal vasculature in ageing.

The determination of vessel supply patterns in the motor cortex is another ongoing application of VDM. Preliminary results of VDM-based motor cortex supply pattern analysis in healthy volunteers have been published with national and international partners (e.g. Jose Bernal, Joanna Wardlaw, Sven Meuth, Ildiko Dunay; shared last author Alexander Dityatev, Solveig Henneicke [née Jandke], Hendrik Mattern)¹⁶. The translation to clinical application, i.e. investigate potential vascular resistance and resilience mechanism in Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), has been funded by the DFG (Project-Nr. 501214112; PIs Stefanie Schreiber, Hendrik Mattern, Oliver Speck) with VDM being an essential part of the analysis.

Beyond arteries, preliminary results of applying VDM to study the interactions of venous vasculature, ageing, and laminar microstructure, i.e. myelin and iron, have been published in a project with Christoph Knoll, Esther Kühn, and colleagues¹⁷. In line with laminar assessment of the human brain, an explorative study with Valentina Perosa, Frank Angenstein, and Christian Mawrin, has been presented during ISMRM 2022, in which VDM and R2* mapping

was applied to ex vivo data acquired at 9.4T to study microstructural and microvascular patterns across cortical depth¹⁸.

Beyond MRI, we applied VDM in microscopy as part of the analysis to study vascular and neural transcriptomics to reveal stage-dependent pathways of inflammation and cognitive dysfunction in a rat model of hypertension. There VDM was used to decipher the spatial interdependencies of astrocytes, microglia, vasculature and blood-brain-barrier breakdown (collaboration with Philipp Ulbrich, Alexander Dityatev, Solveig Henneicke [née Jandke], Michael Sendtner, Ildiko Dunay, and colleagues; preliminary results¹⁹, preprint available²⁰).

1. <https://www.studyforrest.org/>
2. Hanke M, et al. "A studyforrest extension, simultaneous fMRI and eye gaze recordings during prolonged natural stimulation." Scientific data 3.1 (2016): 1-15.
3. Bollmann S, et al. "Imaging of the pial arterial vasculature of the human brain in vivo using high-resolution 7T time-of-flight angiography." eLife, 2022; DOI: 10.7554/eLife.71186
4. <https://osf.io/nr6gc/>; DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/NR6GC
5. <https://gitlab.com/hmattern/omelette>
6. Mattern H "Openly available sMall vEsseL sEgmenTaTion pipeline (OMELETTE)"; 29th Annual Meeting of International Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine. ISMRM, May 2021, virtual meeting
7. SMILE-UHURA challenge and data <https://doi.org/10.7303/syn47164761>
8. <https://github.com/soumickmj/DS6>
9. Chatterjee S, et al. "DS6: Deformation-Aware Semi-Supervised Learning: Application to Small Vessel Segmentation with Noisy Training Data." Journal of Imaging 2022; DOI: 10.3390/jimaging8100259
10. Mattern H, et al. "Vessel distance mapping for deep gray matter structures" 29th Annual Meeting of International Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine. ISMRM, May 2021, virtual meeting
11. Mattern H, Speck O; "Vessel distance mapping" 36th Annual Scientific Meeting of European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology. ESMRMB, September 2020, Online; DOI: 10.1007/s10334-020-00876-y
12. Vessel distance mapping (VDM) source code: <https://github.com/hendrikmattern/VesselDistanceMapping>
13. Mattern H, Speck O; Resolution-dependency of arterial and venous density estimates and vessel distance maps in deep gray matter; Joint Annual Meeting ISMRM-ESMRMB 2022, May 2022, London, UK
14. Mattern H, et al. "Vessel distance mapping reveals mesoscopic arterial and venous patterns in the putamen", Preprint, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8098900>

15. Garcia-Garcia B*, Mattern H*, et al. "Vessel Distance Mapping: A novel methodology for assessing vascular-induced cognitive resilience" *NeuroImage* 2023; DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2023.120094; *equal contribution
16. Schreiber S, et al. "Brain Vascular Health in ALS Is Mediated through Motor Cortex Microvascular Integrity" *Cells* 2023; DOI:10.3390/cells12060957
17. Knoll C, et al. "Age-Related Differences in Human Cortical Microstructure Depend on Distance to Nearest Vein" DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.4435790
18. Mattern H, et al. "Post mortem study of R2* and vessel distance maps across cortical depth" Joint Annual Meeting ISMRM-ESMRMB 2022, May 2022, London, UK
19. Ulbrich P, et al. "Stage-dependent responses of vascular and parenchymal cells in the hypertensive rat brain". 31st European Meeting on Hypertension and Cardiovascular Protection, June 2022, Athens/Hybrid; DOI: 10.1097/01.hjh.0000836812.14897.03
20. Ulbrich P, et al. "Vascular and neural transcriptomics reveal stage-dependent pathways to inflammation and cognitive dysfunction in a rat model of hypertension" DOI: 10.1101/2023.01.20.524921

4 Published project results

4.1 Peer reviewed publications

Full Paper:

1. Garcia-Garcia B*, **Mattern H***, Vockert N, Yakupov R, Schreiber F, Spallazzi M, Perosa V, Haghikia A, Speck O, Düzel E, Maass A, Schreiber S; *Vessel Distance Mapping: A novel methodology for assessing vascular-induced cognitive resilience*; *NeuroImage* 2023; DOI: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2023.120094
*equal contribution; [open access](#)
2. Schreiber S, Bernal J, Arndt P, Schreiber F, Müller P, Morton L, Braun-Dullaeus RC, Valdés-Hernández MC, Duarte R, Wardlaw JM, Meuth SG, Mietzner G, Vielhaber S, Dunay IR, Dityatev A*, Jandke S*, **Mattern H***; *Brain Vascular Health in ALS Is Mediated through Motor Cortex Microvascular Integrity*; *Cells* 2023; DOI:10.3390/cells12060957
*equal contribution; [open access](#)
3. Perosa V, Rotta J, Yakupov R, Kuijf HJ, Schreiber F, Oltmer JT, **Mattern H**, Heinze HJ, Düzel E, Schreiber S; *Implications of quantitative susceptibility mapping at 7 Tesla MRI for microbleeds detection in cerebral small vessel disease*; *Frontiers in Neurology* 2023; DOI: 10.3389/fneur.2023.1112312; [open access](#)
4. Chatterjee S, Prabhu L, Pattadkal M, Bortsova G, Sarasaen C, Dubost F, **Mattern H**, de Bruijne M, Speck O, Nürnberger A; *DS6: Deformation-Aware Semi-Supervised Learning: Application to Small Vessel Segmentation with Noisy Training Data*; *Journal of Imaging* 2022; DOI: 10.3390/jimaging8100259; [open access](#)

5. Bollmann S, **Mattern H**, Bernier M, Robinson SR, Park D, Speck O, Polimeni JR; *Imaging of the pial arterial vasculature of the human brain in vivo using high-resolution 7T time-of-flight angiography*; eLife, 2022; DOI: 10.7554/eLife.71186; [open access](#)
6. Sciarra A, **Mattern H**, Yakupov R, Chatterjee S, Oeltze-Jafra S, Speck O; *Quantitative Evaluation of Prospective Motion Correction in Healthy Subjects at 7T MRI*; Magnetic Resonance in Medicine, 2021; DOI: 10.1002/mrm.28998; [open access](#)
7. Vockert N, Perosa V, Ziegler G, Schreiber F, Priester A, Spallazzi M, Garcia-Garcia B, Aruci M, **Mattern H**, Haghikia A, Düzel E, Schreiber S, Maass A; *Hippocampal vascularization patterns exert local and distant effects on brain structure but not vascular pathology in old age*; Brain Communications, 2021; DOI: 10.1093/braincomms/fcab127; [open access](#)
8. Lüsebrink F, **Mattern H**, Yakupov R, Acosta-Cabronero J, Ashtarayeh M, Oeltze-Jafra S, Speck O; *Comprehensive ultrahigh resolution whole brain in vivo MRI dataset as a human phantom*; Scientific Data, 2021; DOI: 10.1038/s41597-021-00923-w; [open access](#)

Case reports and comments:

1. Schreiber S, Arndt P, Meuth SG, Dityatev A, **Mattern H**; *Brain microvascular disease and functional network connectivity a call for a stage-based approach*; Brain Communications, 2023; DOI:10.1093/braincomms/fcad135; [open access](#)
2. Schreiber S*, John A-C*, Werner C, Vielhaber S, Heinze H-J, Speck O, Würfel J, Behme D*, **Mattern H***; *Counteraction of inflammatory activity in CAA-related subarachnoid hemorrhage*; Journal of Neurology, 2022; DOI:10.1007/s00415-022-11437-9
*equal contribution; [open access](#)

4.2 Further publications and publicly available results

Challenges and workshops:

1. SMILE-UHURA: *Small Vessel Segmentation at Mesoscopic ScaLE from Ultra-High Resolution 7T Magnetic Resonance Angiograms*
Organizers: Chatterjee S, **Mattern H**, Dubost F, Schreiber S, Nürnberger A, Speck O;
Conference: IEEE - ISBI 2023, Cartagena de Indias, Colombia:
<https://doi.org/10.7303/syn47164761>; [open access](#)

Preprints:

1. Mattern H, Garcia-Garcia B, Böwe S, Mietzner G, Henneicke S, Speck O, Schreiber S. "Vessel distance mapping reveals mesoscopic arterial and venous patterns in the putamen", Preprint, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8098900; [open access](#)
2. Knoll C, Döhler J, Northall A, Schreiber S, **Mattern H**, Kuehn E; *Age-Related Differences in Human Cortical Microstructure Depend on Distance to Nearest Vein*; DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.4435790; [open access](#)

3. Ulbrich P, Morton L, Briese M, Lämmlin N, **Mattern H**, Hasanuzzaman Md, Westhues M, Khoshneviszadeh M, Appenzeller S, Gündel D, Toussaint M, Brust P, Kniess T, Oelschlegel A, Goldschmidt J, Meuth S, Heinze HJ, Debska-Vielhaber G, Vielhaber S, Becker A, Dityatev A, Jandke S, Sendtner M, Dunay I, Schreiber S; *Vascular and neural transcriptomics reveal stage-dependent pathways to inflammation and cognitive dysfunction in a rat model of hypertension*; DOI: 10.1101/2023.01.20.524921; [open access](#)

[Open tools, source code, and data:](#)

1. Vessel segmentation source code (OMELETTE): <https://gitlab.com/hmattern/omelette>
2. Vessel distance mapping (VDM) source code: <https://github.com/hendrikmattern/VesselDistanceMapping>
3. Benchmark vessel segmentation data from the SMILE-UHURA challenge: <https://doi.org/10.7303/syn47164761>
4. DS6 vessel segmentation source code: <https://github.com/soumickmj/DS6>
5. Data of the highest resolution ToF angiography to date at 140 μm isotropic resolution: <https://osf.io/nr6gc/> DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/NR6GC

Conference abstracts:

1. Ulbrich P, Morton L, Briese M, Lämmlin N, **Mattern H**, Hasanuzzaman M, Westhues M, Garz C, Becker A, Dityatev A, Jandke S, Yilmazer-Hanke D, Sendtner M, Dunay I, Schreiber S; *Stage-dependent responses of vascular and parenchymal cells in the hypertensive rat brain*; 31st European Meeting on Hypertension and Cardiovascular Protection, June 2022, Athens; DOI: 10.1097/01.hjh.0000836812.14897.03; [open access](#)
2. **Mattern H**, Angenstein F, Mawrin C, Perosa V; *Post mortem study of $R2^*$ and vessel distance maps across cortical depth*; Joint Annual Meeting ISMRM-ESMRMB 2022, May 2022, London, UK
3. **Mattern H**, Speck O; *Resolution-dependency of arterial and venous density estimates and vessel distance maps in deep gray matter*; Joint Annual Meeting ISMRM-ESMRMB 2022, May 2022, London, UK
4. **Mattern H**; *Vessel distance mapping of the aging subcortical venous vasculature*; 37th Annual Scientific Meeting of European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology. ESMRMB, October 2021, Online; DOI: 10.1007/s10334-021-00947-8; [open access](#)
5. **Mattern H**; *Openly available sMall vEsseL sEgmenTaTion pipelinE (OMELETTE)*; 29th Annual Meeting of International Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine. ISMRM, May 2021, virtual meeting
6. **Mattern H**, Schreiber S, Speck O; *Vessel distance mapping for deep gray matter structures*; 29th Annual Meeting of International Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine. ISMRM, May 2021, virtual meeting

7. **Mattern H**, Speck O; *Vessel distance mapping*; 36th Annual Scientific Meeting of European Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine and Biology. ESMRMB, September 2020, Online; DOI: 10.1007/s10334-020-00876-y; [open access](#)

4.3 Patents (pending and granted)

None